

First record of *Sastrapada baerensprungi* (Stål, 1859) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Reduviidae: Stenopodainae) in Croatia

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ABSTRACT: The first record of *Sastrapada baerensprungi* (Stål, 1859) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Reduviidae: Stenopodainae) for Croatia is reported. Information on the known European distribution of the species is summarized.

KEYWORDS: *Sastrapada baerensprungi*, first record, distribution, Croatia, Mediterranean Region.

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The Mediterranean assassin bug *Sastrapada baerensprungi* (Stål, 1859) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Reduviidae: Stenopodainae) is the only member of the genus *Sastrapada* Amyot & Serville, 1843 which is recognized in Europe (Grosso-Silva et al., 2021).

So far, *S. baerensprungi* has been reported from the following European countries: Albania, Bulgaria, France (mainland and Corsica), Greece (mainland and Crete), Italy (mainland, Sardinia and Sicily), Portugal, Spain and Switzerland (Putshkov & Moulet, 2009; Dioli, 2016; Grosso-Silva et al., 2021). The presence of the species in Switzerland is doubtful: The only record, from Geneva, might be a result of a passive transport (Dioli, 2016).

Now, the first record of *S. baerensprungi* in Croatia can be reported: On 14.09.2018, a female specimen was photographed by Jurica Stošić near the village of Lopar, located in the northern part of the island of Rab in the Adriatic Sea (Fig. 1).

The photograph was uploaded to the online database iNaturalist (Stošić, 2019).

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Figure 1. *Sastrapada baerensprungi* (Stål, 1859), female, near Lopar, Rab, Croatia, 14.09.2018. (Photo: Jurica Stošić).